

Suicide Prevention: A Global Imperative for Protecting Lives and Sustaining Human Well-being

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As the cases of suicide increase day by day, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic, suicide prevention has become an immediate need globally. It not only ends the life of the victims but also affects the mental health of other associated and non-associated people. The present study taps into how suicide has a ripple effect on the people surrounding (parents, siblings, peers, educators, and mental health practitioners). The study further explores the intersection of suicide prevention with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and it also highlights different national and international policies on suicide. The findings underscore that effective suicide prevention demands a coordinated, multisectoral, and evidence-based response that engages governments, communities, educators, and international organisations. Addressing suicide as a shared societal responsibility, rather than an isolated individual failure, is essential to achieving meaningful and sustainable progress toward global mental health equity.

Keywords: Suicide prevention, COVID-19, SDGs, policies and plans of suicide, mental health, ripple effects

Suicide is not only a Loss of a Person, but Loss of a Nation

Suicide prevention is an immediate need globally, as it not only ends the life of the victims but also affects the mental health of other associated and non-associated people. Death by suicide leads to a huge burden on the macro level. According to the study, 161,349 years of labor and about 4 lakh years of life are lost, which means wealthy countries lose a substantial number of human resources (Doran & Kinchin, 2020). In addition to this, there is a significant financial loss; the projected cost of lost earning potential due to youth suicide is US\$5.534 billion (Doran & Kinchin, 2020). The suicide of a child leads to family dysfunction in terms of decreased communication and adaptation, and less parental love and affection expressed to the siblings (Cerel et al., 2008). Social relationships and networking of the bereaved family deteriorate as these families fear the upsetting judgment and hence avoid them. Clinical evidence suggests long-term effects on everyone in the family, especially children, and psychological development (Rogers et al., 2008). Parents, without knowing the actual cause of their child's suicide, blame themselves, misunderstand, avoid, and withdraw from social networks (Séguin et al., 1995). Siblings of bereaved children face mental health issues (anxiety disorders, self-harming tendencies, PTSD, & traumatic sorrow); functional issues (such as social issues or academic challenges), and physical health issues (such as the beginning or worsening of disease). Annually, sibling suicide kills up to 8,000 youngsters in the US (Cerel et al., 2008). The suicide of a

person impacts the professional career of psychiatrists and psychologists. According to a study, nearly 40% of psychiatrists stated that they face difficulty with clinical work for 1 week to 6 months after the suicide of a patient (Gibbons et al., 2019). The suicide of a student can impact the personal (poor sleep) as well as the professional career (lower self-confidence) of the teachers (Kölves et al., 2017) (See figure 1). Hence, suicide behavior is very complex and can impact more people surrounding immediate suicide prevention strategies and intervention needs to be given to all the stakeholders to reduce the number of suicide cases.

Figure 1

Ripple Effect of Suicide Loss

Note. (Source: Based on the review, author generated the image using AI)

Increasing Suicide Rates After Covid-19: How & why?

Suicide has always been an issue of global concern; however, data

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suggest a noticeable increase in suicide cases after the novel COVID-19 pandemic. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, nearly 40.0 million students in Bangladesh were impacted directly or indirectly (Emon, 2020). Studies show that due to prolonged dis-attached to the academic environment and educational setting, students indulge in problematic behavior such as difficulties in sleep, lack of appetite, including crime, drug use, internet gaming, stress, worry, and suicidal thoughts (Daria & Islam, 2022). A study comparing the number of students' suicides before and after the pandemic, it was found that there was a threefold increase in suicide cases during the COVID-19 epidemic (Daria & Islam, 2022). Experts stated that due to the closing of schools and colleges during a pandemic, students do not get the opportunity to play or spend time with friends, which restricts their feelings from sharing and consequently leads to frustration, violence, suicidal, and abusive behavior (Islam & Hossain, 2021).

Although there was an online education alternative to school education, it was not successful initially, as students from primary and secondary grades used to remain absent from most of the classes (Goto et al., 2022). Studies have also found that students also committed suicide because they were unable to access online education, and secondly, they face difficulty coping with online learning methodology (Khadse et al., 2022). After the pandemic, there is a significant increase in the usage of digital learning and use of smartphones, leading to a distressful situation. There is a significant lack of knowledge and resources for online learning, and many socio-economically disadvantaged students are unable to afford smartphones or laptops, making it difficult for them to continue their studies (Khadse et al., 2022). Adult students faced extreme problems, many of them have experienced financial hardship as a result of the pandemic's decline in their parents' income and the difficulty in finding jobs for their tuition fees (Hosen et al., 2022). Additionally, last year, students had to deal with the difficulty of job searching in the midst of a decrease in economic activity (Fuse-Nagase et al., 2021). All these circumstances make students hopeless for the future; some experience mental health issues and suicidal thoughts. However, a very small number of studies have depicted a reduced number of suicide cases during the epidemic, probably because students get time to stay at home with families (Deisenhammer & Kemmler, 2021). But this study was also based on the first 6 months of the pandemic period; more research needs to be done to establish this fact.

Suicide Prevention and SDG or Sustainable Development Goals

Suicide is a global burden and hence it has also been targeted by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2015. SDGs emphasize "Leaving no one behind"; consequently, various goals and targets are included (17 goals & 169 targets) to achieve this aim. Although Millennium Development Goals 2000-2015 (MDGs) didn't focus on the reduction of suicide death, however, SDGs have fulfilled this gap by including the suicide-related target (Minas et al., 2015). Goal 3 of the SDGs, which deals with "Ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages," covers suicide-related concerns. Suicide mortality has been included in Goal 3, target 3.4.2. (Noncommunicable diseases & mental health) (World Health Organisation, n.d.) directly however there are many other Goals which although not directly related but somehow connected to

suicide behaviour these are SDG 1 (No Poverty: Financial stress & poverty are known risk factors for suicide), SDG 4 (Quality Education: Building adolescents' socio-emotional skills aids suicide prevention), SDG 5 (Gender Equality) & SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals: Collaboration among governments, professional bodies, private entities to advance mental health care worldwide) (Da Costa et al., 2022; Hsu et al., 2019) (see figure 2). The recommendation that has been given by the SDGs and which needs to be followed by member countries is that it is necessary to prevent, treat, and promote mental health and well-being in order to reduce one-third of premature death from non-communicable diseases by 2030. As an effect of the adoption of suicide in SDGs, there is a raise in suicide-related literature by the year 2017-2018, which was very low before 2015 (the year of adoption of SDGs) (Da Costa et al., 2022; Bantjes et al., 2016). People's attention is also directed toward healthcare policies, which were lacking previously. A study shows that after 2015, there is a slight but significant rise in the literature on suicide prevention and healthcare facilities (Da Costa et al., 2022). Increased awareness has led the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the United Nations (UN) to release significant policy documents on the significance of mental health for overall health.

Figure 2
Showing how SDGs are Related to Suicide Prevention

Note. (Source: Based on the review, author generated the image using AI)

Suicide Prevention is an Immediate Need in India but Lacking Necessities

The majority of suicide research in India has focused on variables such as the prevalence of suicide, risk factors, including psychological and demographic risk and methods of suicide (Ram et al., 2022). But literature in terms of suicide prevention strategy or intervention in India is hardly available. There are certain reasons behind India's lacking of suicide prevention strategy and intervention they are, firstly, Suicide procedures, perspectives, prevention tactics, and other aspects that are prevalent in the Western culture may not work in India (Ram et al., 2022), hence before using the intervention a huge adaptation, translation, back-translation and pilot testing for feasibility is to be done which is really challenging (Pathare et al., 2020). Secondly, lack of identification. Suicide intervention is given to those at risk of

suicide, but in India, the identification of suicidal people is very poor; no prior steps are taken to prevent suicide. Thirdly, the criminalisation status of suicide. It was in 2017 that the Mental Healthcare Act (MHCA) was passed, which decriminalized suicide in India. Before this act, it was a crime and consequently, people who attempted suicide were punished by the law (Jacob, 2022). The legal status of suicide blocks distressed people from seeking help and sharing their suicidal thoughts with professionals out of fear of being legally punished, hence they end their lives without any treatment. Fourthly, suicide stigma, according to a study, suicide stigma can slow healthy recovery and lead to poor treatment outcomes (Wellness and Health Promotion, n.d.). Due to public negative opinion towards mental health, people with distressed thoughts avoid suicide-related treatment and intervention. Fifth, Data Insufficiency, the quality of governmental data is insufficient to draw any medical findings or create any guidelines. (Ransing et al., 2022) (see figure 3). WHO has suggested to all Asian countries including India, that suicide can be prevented by limiting the lethal means, educating the gatekeepers, and improving the treatment of various mental health issues (Ram et al., 2022). But unfortunately, in India, there are very few people, NGOs, or institutional divisions who solely focused on preventing suicide, which is insufficient to satisfy the needs of the nation. It is astonishing that suicide prevention programs are lacking even in India's best healthcare institutions. Despite all these barriers, Indian government has presented India's first National Suicide Prevention Strategy on 21st November 2022, after the 5 years of decriminalization of suicide (Ransing et al., 2023).

Figure 3

Barriers in Suicide Prevention in Indian Context

Note. (Source: Based on the review, author generated the image using AI)

Suicide Behaviour and Suicide Ideation: Suicide Ideation as a Crucial Stage to Prevent Suicide

As per DSM-5, suicidal behavior consists of three (3) stages, which move from thoughts to actions. These hierarchical stages are suicide ideation (thoughts & ideas related to suicide behavior), suicide attempt (practical implication of suicide thoughts), and finally, suicide attempt (completed suicide (Caballero-Domínguez & Campo-Arias, 2020). Suicide ideation is a significant stage for

preventing suicide, as it is the initial stage and seen as an early indicator of future suicide attempts and deaths (Arria et al., 2009). Suicide ideation deals with only thoughts, ideas, and wishes, sometimes planning related to suicide behavior, and no practical application is done (Indiana Youth Institute, 2023). It is always better to take an active intervention strategy to prevent suicidal behavior at this initial stage. Secondly, studies show that an unsuccessful suicide attempt is a high risk of complete suicide. This is because the victim now knows all the characteristics of a suicide attempt, such as well-planning and arrangement of lethal means, which increases the likelihood of a suicide attempt (Runeson et al., 2010). Thirdly, preventing suicide after the unsuccessful attempt is made is quite difficult, as the victim is now in a high-risk zone where professional healthcare is needed, and it also involves a huge cost burden (Park et al., 2018). Hence, it is always good to stop the suicidal behavior at its initial stage before any attempts have been made.

Initiatives to Prevent Suicide Behaviour

From time to time, the issue of suicide has been raised and various policies and plans have been made to prevent suicidal behaviour. There are some such policies and plans mentioned below:

Global Laws and Policies to Prevent Suicide

Garrett Lee Smith Memorial Act (GLSMA): The alarming rate of child suicide and mental health crises prompted the way establishing the Garrett Lee Smith Memorial Act (GLSMA) (Goldston et al., 2010). In memory of Garrett Lee Smith, the son of former Oregon Senator Gordon Smith, who tragically died by suicide at the age of 21, the Act was signed into law on October 21, 2004, by President Bush. Garrett's passing made clear how urgently comprehensive suicide prevention measures are needed, especially for young people (Goldston et al., 2010).

Basic Act on Suicide Prevention (2006, amended 2016): This Act was passed in 2006 in Japan, which identifies suicide as a societal problem that may be avoided and places national responsibility for prevention measures. All local governments are requested to develop specialised programs for preventing suicide by the 2016 amendment. It increases awareness, supports mental health services, and encourages early intervention (Nakanishi et al., 2014).

WHO Mental Health Action Plan (2013-2030). A global program aims to improve mental health systems, encourage mental wellbeing, and lessen the burden of mental diseases, including suicide. Enhancing leadership and governance for mental health, offering comprehensive and community-based mental health services, putting promotion and preventive techniques into practice, and bolstering mental health data and research are its four main goals (Mental Health, Brain Health & Substance Use (MSD), 2021).

The LIVE LIFE Implementation Guide (2021). According to the guideline, there are four main ways to prevent suicide: restricting access to resources, promoting responsible media coverage, educating young people about life skills, and identifying and helping those who are at risk early. With the help of six pillars, it offers a workable framework for nations looking to lower suicide rates and meet global mental health goals by 2030 (Thomson, 2022).

Indian Legal Policies against Suicide

Several innovative measures have been implemented in recent years to lower India's rising suicide rate. Suicide prevention in India

involves a combination of government initiatives, legal reforms, and support from NGOs. Some of the suicide prevention initiatives are mentioned below:

UMMEED Guidelines of India (2023). In 2023, India's Ministry of Health and Family Welfare launched UMMEED Guidelines, a useful framework for suicide prevention that aims to empower frontline workers like teachers, community leaders, ASHA workers, and basic healthcare practitioners. The guidelines, which were developed with assistance from organisations including NIMHANS and AIIMS, emphasise community-based support, basic counselling skills, early identification of those at risk of suicide, and clear referral channels (Mehrotra et al., 2025).

Mental Healthcare Act, 2017. It was a significant piece of legislation that altered India's approach to mental health and suicide prevention. The decriminalisation of suicide attempts under Section 115, which acknowledges that people who attempt suicide are probably experiencing extreme stress or mental illness and require care rather than punishment, is one of its most noteworthy features. The Act requires the government to offer mental health treatment, rehabilitation, and assistance to such individuals (Chandrashekar et al., 2018)

National Suicide Prevention Strategy (NSPS) (2022). It was India's first comprehensive program by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, launched in November 2022 with an aim of reducing suicide mortality by 10% by 2030. It highlighted that by the next three years, a system for suicide surveillance must be established; by five years, every district must develop psychiatric outpatient departments through the District Mental Health Program; and all educational institutions must implement a mental health curriculum (Singh, 2023).

KIRAN Helpline (2020). In 2020, the Indian Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment launched the KIRAN Helpline (1800-599-0019) as a toll-free, 24-hour mental health support service. Its objective is to provide emergency psychiatric treatment to anyone experiencing mental distress, particularly those who are at risk of suicide. The helpline is staffed by trained mental health professionals and offers support in 13 Indian languages, ensuring widespread accessibility (Agrawal & Agrawal, 2020).

Centre for Mental Health Law and Policy (CMHLP) (2007). It was established in 2007 as a well-known organization in India, committed to improving mental health wellness using a community-focused, rights-based approach. To promote mental health and prevent suicide, it works with a variety of stakeholders, including legislators, mental health specialists, civil society organizations, and people with lived experience (Centre for Mental Health Law & Policy, 2026).

Decriminalising Suicide in India. Focusing on the Indian Constitution Act, Article 21, which states the right to life or liberty, doesn't support suicide attempts. The act states that nobody may be deprived of their life or personal freedom unless the legal process is followed. Hence, this article clearly indicates the right to life and doesn't speak for the right to die (Ranjan et al., 2014). Another Legislation regarding suicide is the IPC section 309, formulated in 1860 under the British Raj Regime, which criminalises suicide attempt and recommends imprisonment for the punishment of imprison for maximum 1 year or a fine or both (Ganguli et al., 2025).

Conclusion

Suicide records are significantly worsened in the aftermath of the

COVID-19 pandemic due to widespread social isolation, economic hardship, and disrupted mental health services, but it's important to note that suicide is not only an individual loss but its ripple effect has negative consequences on the people around. The gravity of this issue has prompted sustained responses from national governments and international organisations alike. The United Nations, through its Sustainable Development Goals, formally recognised suicide prevention as a global priority by embedding suicide mortality reduction as Indicator 3.4.2 under SDG 3, with a target to reduce such deaths by one third by 2030. Lastly, the prevention of suicide is possible if the responsibility is shared among the people at the personal level, local level, national level, and international level.

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